

Safe reinforcement learning for ship energy management optimization with LLM-based reward shaping

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Abstract—Cruise ships are large greenhouse gas emitters. Given the net-zero emission goal by 2050 set by the International Maritime Organization, it is crucial to focus on different strategies for reducing emissions. One promising strategy is to work on reducing energy losses due to non-optimal management of a cruise ship’s complex energy system. Effectively managing a ship’s energy consumption is a difficult task. Modern reinforcement learning approaches have been employed to the task at hand. Results have shown improvements over traditional optimization methods that fail to scale to large stochastic problems such as ship energy optimization. However, reinforcement learning approaches lack a direct focus on ensuring the safety of the system, which is critical for a real-world application.

This paper showcases work in progress related to developing a safe reinforcement learning (RL) framework for ship energy optimization. We utilize a formal safety shield to block unsafe control actions and a large language model (LLM) to generate a reward function (RF) that incorporates safety constraints. We construct a white-box physical system of a ship’s energy management system and a faster black-box surrogate model as environments to train and test our RL methods. Preliminary results show that the integration of the safety shield and the LLM-generated reward function is promising in reducing safety violations.

Index Terms—reinforcement learning, generative AI, energy management, energy optimization, large language models, reward shaping

I. INTRODUCTION

Shipping is the most important mode of transportation of goods by volume, as 80% of the world’s trade volume is carried by sea [1]. At the same time, maritime vessels are responsible for 2.9% of global CO₂ emissions and up to 4% of CO₂ emissions at EU level [2]. The current greenhouse gas strategy of the International Maritime Organization (IMO), has set the goal of net-zero emissions by or around 2050 [2]. Meeting the defined goal would require improvement in different areas of shipping.

Passenger transport ships, especially cruise ships, have a large potential for optimization. A cruise vessel’s main purpose is to entertain the passengers on board. As such, the hotel system that regulates passenger comfort and entertainment makes up a large part of the consumed energy. The HVAC system, part of the hotel system, is one of the biggest consumers on board that utilizes almost 30% of total energy [3].

Managing the ship hotel system can be challenging due to the complexity of managing multiple interconnected parts

and due to unpredictable factors, such as passenger behavior and weather. Traditional optimization methods, such as linear programming, are shown to fail at tackling complex stochastic problems [4]. Modern methods, namely reinforcement learning (RL) methods, are better suited for sequential decision problems with large uncertainty.

Ships are safety-critical systems governed by explicit regulations. The hotel system inside the ship must be operated such that temperature, humidity, and CO₂ levels inside the ship do not exceed safe ranges. Traditional RL methods often struggle to ensure the safety of the optimized system [5]. This paper focuses on the development of a safe RL system for ship energy management in two directions. The first direction is utilizing a safety shield, which prevents the agent from conducting actions that lead to unsafe states. Secondly, the reward function penalizes the agent if it has entered unsafe states, thus teaching it to avoid them in the future.

The reward function specifies if the behavior of the RL agent should be rewarded or penalized. Generating a good reward function for an RL agent, also known as reward shaping, can be challenging and often requires an experienced engineer [6]. A good reward function should reward the agent for preliminary steps to achieve the given goal. We investigate the use of a large language model (LLM) to generate the reward function.

This paper is structured as follows. Section II introduces relevant papers to our work. Section III describes the methodology employed and showcases preliminary results. Section IV presents the conclusion of the paper and outlines future work.

II. STATE OF THE ART

There is existing research on the topic of ship energy optimization. Traditional methods such as linear programming or genetic algorithms (GA) are shown to be effective at optimizing static problems with defined variables. Papers [7] and [8] showcase the use of genetic algorithms, namely Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) for ship energy optimization.

Reinforcement learning based methods are not restricted by the size of the search space as traditional methods are. Furthermore, they can learn to deal with real-time challenges and setbacks. As such, they are suited to the problem of ship energy management system (EMS) optimization. In [4]

a deep RL algorithm was employed, namely proximal policy optimization (PPO), to optimize ship energy management over different operational conditions. They were able to achieve fuel efficiency improvement of up to 10 % over traditional optimization methods. Other works, such as [9] and [10], have used deep RL to optimize hotel and propulsion loads for hydrogen hybrid ships. While research demonstrates the potential of reinforcement learning for ship energy optimization, there is a lack of focus on safety and formal safety constraints.

Safe reinforcement learning is a subfield of RL focused on learning optimal policies that comply with safety constraints. In [11] an extension to the regular PPO algorithm was developed, named Penalized Proximal Policy Optimization (P3O), which performs better at satisfying safety constraints than regular PPO. P3O deconstructs the reward signal into a reward signal focused on improving the goal and a cost signal that penalizes unsafe behavior. Another approach for safe RL is shielding. Papers [12] and [13] implement a shielding mechanism that calculates the probability of an action being unsafe and prevents the agent from taking unsafe actions.

A crucial part of applying a reinforcement learning method is reward shaping. Traditionally, rewards have been shaped by an engineer, a process that requires experience and can be time-consuming. Recent papers have shown the potential of using large language models (LLMs) for reward function generation. In [6], Text2Reward is introduced, a framework for turning natural language goals into dense reward codes written in Python. The approach relies on a human feedback loop to evaluate the performance of the reward function. [6] prompted GPT4 and achieved better results than hand-crafted reward signals in multiple control environments.

Our work builds upon previous work on ship energy management system (EMS) optimization by focusing on safe RL approaches with LLM-based reward signal generation.

III. METHODOLOGY

As part of the methodology of this paper, an RL controller system was developed, consisting of the following parts: a white-box simulation of a ship’s microgrid energy system, a black-box surrogate model, a reward function generator, an RL controller, and a safety shield. Fig. 1 gives a schematic look into the methodology of this paper. The white-box simulation defines a physical representation of a ship’s hotel system. Based on the white-box model, a faster black-box approximated model was developed. This surrogate model, alongside a battery model and a load curve, make up the ship’s microgrid environment. An RL agent was developed to interact with the environment. It utilizes a reward function that is generated by an LLM reward function generator (RFG). While the agent interacts with the environment, a safety shield is deployed to block unsafe actions during inference. After the agent has been trained, performance data is fed back to the LLM to improve the reward function generation.

Fig. 1. Methodology of our work.

A. White-box simulation

The simulation of a ship’s microgrid energy system is composed of models for consumption, storage, and generation. The consumption simulation model is developed in IDA ICE, a building simulator software, and consists of 4 cabins and the hallway in between. The simulation models the thermal properties of the compartments, the HVAC system that serves the compartments, the lighting system, passenger occupancy, weather, and electrical consumption. The simulation includes real weather data and realistic occupancy data. A battery model was also developed in Simulink in order to simulate storage, and a load curve was used for approximating generation. While all the parts are finished, their integration is ongoing.

B. Black-box surrogate simulation

The white-box simulation is time-consuming to run. Thus, we developed a faster black-box surrogate model based on it. To train the surrogate model, we extracted simulations from the white-box model. Due to the computational cost of running the white-box model, we only extracted a limited number of simulations. The simulations were produced using a grid search on independent variables. The following were used as independent variables for the simulation: air handling unit (AHU) temperature setpoint, AHU humidity setpoint, compartment maximum temperature setpoint, compartment minimum temperature setpoint, and inflow setpoint. After discarding the simulations that failed, we were left with a dataset of 143 simulations, each simulation spanning a year of data. We trained a deep neural network on data from 80% of the dataset, or 114 simulations. The outputs of the surrogate model are the electric power of different systems, such as the boiler, chiller, conditioner fans, fan coil units, pumps, lighting system, and compartment sensor data such as air temperature, humidity and CO₂ levels for a specific timestep.

Multiple architectures for the surrogate model were tested on the remaining 29 test simulations, and the root mean squared error (RMSE) was used as a performance metric. The architecture of the best-performing model is a neural network consisting of 5 linear layers and rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation functions in between. The RMSE score of the best-performing architecture can be seen in Table I. To calculate the RMSE, the outputs of the surrogate model were treated as a timeseries and compared with the white box simulation outputs with identical inputs. The RMSE was computed in the

normalized space to prevent any variable from dominating. We report the mean over each dependent variable, test simulation, and standard deviation over different test simulations. An RMSE of 0.06 in our case can be explained as each output of the surrogate model being on average 0.06 standard deviations away from the correct value.

TABLE I
RMSE SCORE OF BEST PERFORMING SURROGATE MODEL

RMSE mean	RMSE standard deviation
0.061	0.021

C. Reinforcement learning algorithm

A reinforcement learning environment was built on top of the surrogate model. Currently, as the integration of the different parts of the ship’s microgrid is ongoing, the environment is comprised of only the surrogate model. Thus, the current objective for the RL algorithm is the management of the control actions to decrease the hotel load while incurring as few safety violations as possible.

We implemented two reinforcement learning agents, a PPO agent and a P3O agent. The agents take as input the ship’s EMS state (electrical power, compartment temperature, CO₂, humidity) at a particular timestep and select the control actions. The observation space is continuous while the action space is discretized into 10 bins. The actor and the critic are implemented as neural network architectures. The actor outputs the logit probabilities of each possible action choice for the action from the discrete space. The action is then sampled from the distribution. Both our PPO and P3O implementations are similar. P3O builds upon PPO by decoupling the cost from the reward function and adding an extra loss term based on the cost advantage [11].

D. Reward function generation

Reward shaping is a crucial part of solving a reinforcement learning problem. We experimented with both handcrafted and LLM-generated reward functions. The handcrafted reward signal was shaped using our knowledge of the task. The LLM used for reward function generation was GPT4. The input prompt to the LLM is composed of four parts. Firstly, the environment description describes background knowledge about the environment and the task at hand. The environment description includes a natural language description of the environment, the Python code of the environment class, a description of the actions and observation spaces, and the format of the inputs and outputs of the function. Secondly, the optimization goal defines the goal to be achieved, in this case, reducing energy consumption. Thirdly, the safety and controller constraints were included in the prompt. The constraints were derived from a System Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) of the environment. Finally, the last part of the prompt is the feedback history defined by user feedback. Our methodology for reward function generation is iterative. After a reward function was generated and the agent finished

training, we added feedback regarding the performance of the agent to the feedback history and generated another reward function. The iterative process goes on until the LLM is unable to generate a better reward function despite the feedback.

E. Safety shield mechanism

To enforce safe behavior from the RL agent, we developed a safety shield. The shield has two main roles. Firstly, it makes use of conditional logic and the system’s safety constraints to determine the number of safety violations during each episode of the training or testing of the RL agent. One example of such violations includes the compartment temperature being below the safe range. Secondly, it serves the purpose of blocking actions it believes are unsafe during inference. If an action is blocked, the agent samples another action. As the agents in this work learn a stochastic policy, resampling at inference is possible. A threshold of 20 new samples was set in order to avoid situations where unsafe actions are inevitable.

IV. INITIAL RESULTS

To test our safe reinforcement learning methodology, we ran several experiments, the results of which can be seen in Tables II-III. Each row represents the mean and standard deviation of 100 test episodes. Each test episode is a random 24-hour period in a year. We used open-loop control as a baseline to compare the efficacy of our RL methods. Temperature and humidity setpoints were set within safe ranges, while airflow was restricted to the minimum safe amount to reduce energy consumption.

TABLE II
INITIAL RESULTS OF REINFORCEMENT LEARNING EXPERIMENTS

Algorithm	Power consumption	Safety violations
Open loop control	7.0 ± 2.5 MWh	388.5 ± 151
PPO	3.6 ± 1.4 MWh	405.6 ± 121.5
P3O	6.7 ± 3.3 MWh	167.0 ± 139.8

TABLE III
INITIAL RESULTS OF INTEGRATING THE SAFETY SHIELD AND THE LLM-BASED REWARD FUNCTION

Algorithm	Power consumption	Safety violations
P3O	6.7 ± 3.3 MWh	167.0 ± 139.8
P3O + LLM RF	10.9 ± 4.6 MWh	72.1 ± 83.7
P3O + shield	6.4 ± 3.0 MWh	64.4 ± 55.5
P3O + shield + LLM RF	11.5 ± 4.8 MWh	48.9 ± 47.7

The RL agents were trained for 1000 episodes, each episode representing a 24-hour period. Each agent was trained 3 times using different seeds to reduce the stochasticity introduced from training. We report the mean and standard deviation over 100 test episodes averaged over the 3 runs. The safety shield kept track of the violations during training and testing and blocked unsafe actions only during testing. Some experiments use a large language model reward function (LLM RF), following the methodology described. The LLM-based RF used for the results shown in Table III was generated after three

iterations. It is worth noting from the setup of our experiments that newer LLMs such as GPT4 are very effective at generating reward functions. GPT4 was able to produce a syntactically correct RF that performed well from the first iteration. The follow-up iterations consisted of minor adjustments.

From the initial results, several takeaways support our ongoing work. From Table II we can see that the PPO agent achieves a much better performance in energy efficiency than open-loop control, showcasing the strength of RL optimization. However, PPO was unable to reduce safety violations, validating the need for safety-focused methods. The P3O agent is the best-performing algorithm with regards to safety, reducing the number of safety violations to less than half of PPO or open-loop control.

We believe that P3O performs better in problems where two conflicting objectives need to be optimized, in our case, energy consumption and safety violations. For PPO, both objectives are combined into a single scalar reward. Thus, PPO is highly dependent on the weighting of each objective during reward shaping. We believe that is the case in the results shown in Table II, where the agent focused more heavily on optimizing energy than safety.

Furthermore, from Table III we can see the results of integrating the safety shield and the LLM-generated RF with our P3O implementation. Both additions lead to an improvement in safety violations, with the best-performing experiment utilizing both. These components act as guardrails that help keep the policy of the agent on track. One thing to note is that while safety violations go down with more guardrails added, power consumption goes up. As the agent is more restricted in the actions that it can choose, it will start choosing actions that are safer but suboptimal for energy optimization.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Reducing energy consumption and emissions for the cruise ship industry is more important than ever. Reinforcement learning based methods have been shown to be reliable at tackling ship energy optimization, but do not have an explicit focus on safety. The current work has outlined a method for applying safe reinforcement learning methods to the challenge at hand, the initial results of which were presented in this paper.

However, the results are limited by several factors, which are to be addressed in future work. Firstly, the results shown in this paper only apply to the management of the surrogate consumption model. We plan to run experiments on the full ship microgrid that is made of the white box simulation model, the battery, and generation to better reflect real-world conditions. Moreover, the results shown apply only to a reference cruise ship. Future work on different types of ships could be explored to show that the methodology is adaptable. Furthermore, we believe that the work on LLM-based reward shaping has promise and could be investigated in more detail. We plan to experiment with other LLMs such as LLama and Mistral alongside smaller models and compare their performance to the task at hand.

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REFERENCES

- [1] European Commission, "International cooperation and coordination in maritime transport," https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-modes/maritime/international-cooperation-and-coordination_en, n.d., eU Transport.
- [2] —, "Reducing emissions in the shipping sector," https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/transport/reducing-emissions-shipping-sector_en, n.d., (accessed May 20, 2025).
- [3] M. Aarnio, *Cruise Ship Handbook*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2022.
- [4] M. Alshareef and A. F. Alghanmi, "Optimizing maritime energy efficiency: A machine learning approach using deep reinforcement learning for eexi and cii compliance," *Sustainability*, vol. 16, p. 10534, 2024.
- [5] D. Amodei, C. Olah, J. Steinhardt, P. Christiano, J. Schulman, and D. Mané, "Concrete problems in ai safety," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1606.06565*, 2016.
- [6] T. Xie *et al.*, "Text2reward: Automated dense reward function generation for reinforcement learning," in *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2024 (07/05/2024-11/05/2024, Vienna, Austria), 2024.
- [7] Z. Yang, W. Qu, and J. Zhuo, "Optimization of energy consumption in ship propulsion control under severe sea conditions," *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, vol. 12, no. 9, p. 1461, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse12091461>
- [8] X. Wang, H. Zhu, X. Luo, S. Chang, and X. Guan, "A novel optimal dispatch strategy for hybrid energy ship power system based on the improved nsga-ii algorithm," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 232, p. 110385, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2024.110385>
- [9] Y. Zhao, S. Wen, Q. Zhao, B. Zhang, and Y. Huang, "Deep reinforcement learning-based energy management strategy for green ships considering photovoltaic uncertainty," *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 3, p. 565, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse13030565>
- [10] W. Jung and D. Chang, "Deep reinforcement learning-based energy management for liquid hydrogen-fueled hybrid electric ship propulsion system," *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 10, p. 2007, 2023, published: 18 October 2023; Corrected: 14 March 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11102007>
- [11] L. Zhang, L. Shen, L. Yang, S. Chen, X. Wang, B. Yuan, and D. Tao, "Penalized proximal policy optimization for safe reinforcement learning," in *Proceedings of the Thirty-First International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI-22)*, L. D. Raedt, Ed. International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence Organization, 7 2022, pp. 3744–3750, main Track. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.24963/ijcai.2022/520>
- [12] B. Könighofer, R. Akrouf, E. Bartocci, M. Chmelík, and L. Bortolussi, "Online shielding for reinforcement learning," *Innovations in Systems and Software Engineering*, vol. 19, pp. 47–58, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11334-022-00445-3>
- [13] N. Jansen *et al.*, "Safe reinforcement learning using probabilistic shields," in *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Concurrency Theory (CONCUR 2020)*, 2020.